

Figure S1. Daily walking activity (steps/d: **A**) and walking time (minutes/d: **B**) of cows vaccinated on the day of dry-off (d 0) and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**CON**), cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**EV**) and cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a capsule containing meloxicam at 1 mg/kg BW on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**EV+NSAID**). Sample size: $n = 42$ cows per treatment. No effects of parity and treatment (**Trt**) \times parity were detected ($P > 0.15$). Error bars represent SEM.

Figure S2. Hematological parameters of cows vaccinated on the day of dry-off (d 0) and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**CON**), cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**EV**) and cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a capsule containing meloxicam at 1 mg/kg BW on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (**EV+NSAID**). Parameters included (A) eosinophil count, (B) basophil count, (C) red blood cell count, (D) hemoglobin concentration, (E) platelet counts, (F) mean platelet volume (MPV). Sample size: $n = 30$ cows per treatment. ^{a,b}at a time point different letters differ ($P < 0.05$). No effects of treatment (**Trt**) by parity or treatment by parity by day were detected ($P > 0.17$). Error bars represent SEM.

Figure S3. Bovine neutrophil migration measured in a Transwell assay: spontaneous migration (SMP), interleukin-8–induced migration (IL-8 MP), and total migration (TMP). Neutrophils were isolated on d +3 relative to dry-off from cows vaccinated on the day of dry-off (d 0) and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (CON), cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a placebo capsule on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (EV) and cows vaccinated 14 day before dry-off and orally administered a capsule containing meloxicam at 1 mg/kg BW on d 0 and +3 relative to dry-off (EV+NSAID). **Trt** = treatment. Error bars represent SEM.

